

TECHNOLOGIES OF MUTUAL COOPERATION IN PROVIDING ECOLOGICAL AND LEGAL EDUCATION TO YOUTH STUDENTS.

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Annotation: This article discusses the scientific and theoretical aspects of school-family and community cooperation in the field of environmental education and their practical significance, and analyzes the results of the experimental process. The cooperation of the mahalla with the school on environmental and legal issues and the scientific and practical aspects of its management process.

Keywords: Ecology, nature, man and society, law, norms, school, family and community cooperation, global environmental security, environmental and legal education, "ECOSAN" Ecology and health, harmony between nature and man.

One of the priorities in achieving the stability of the system of nature-society-human-technology relations in solving global problems is to further strengthen the cooperation of schools, families and communities in environmental and legal education of young people. After all, today's youth of more than 2 billion people need to constantly improve the activities of socio-political institutions, including school, family and community, which are responsible for raising their legal awareness, in particular, the process of environmental and legal education. In particular, in the context of increasing demand for natural resources to meet the needs of society, increasing anthropotechnogenic pressure on nature, the escalation of international environmental and political relations, some of our students develop

a sense of nature, in general, the problem of global environmental security without improving environmental education very difficult to do.

The chosen topic in this regard shows that it is relevant and necessary based on the needs of society. Today, based on the international principles of environmental protection, Uzbekistan is gradually implementing democratic reforms based on the principle of "from a strong state to a strong civil society", taking the necessary measures to address social and environmental problems and educating students in educational institutions. It is expedient to enrich the consciousness with knowledge that reveals the essence of current environmental problems and to strengthen this knowledge through their practical activities, social work. In accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" adopted on September 23, 2020, and President Sh.M. In his speech at the ceremony dedicated to the Day of Teachers and Coaches on September 30, 2020, Mirziyoyev said: in other words, they must be the leading representatives of our time and society."¹ Clause 5.1 of the Action Strategy of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021"² also states that "prevention of environmental problems that harm the environment, public health and gene pool."

The topic of "Improving the cooperation of school, family and community in the formation of concepts of environmental and legal education of students" shows the need for insufficient research and separate research, taking into account local conditions and characteristics. The main purpose of the study is to develop proposals and recommendations for improving the cooperation of school, family and community in environmental and legal education of schoolchildren.

The main tasks of the subject:

¹ Speech by President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the Day of Teachers and Coaches

² Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017, No. 6, Article 70

-analysis of the process of improving the cooperation of school, family and community in environmental and legal education of schoolchildren and coverage of the content of spiritual and moral education;

- identification of theoretical knowledge, practical skills and competencies to improve the cooperation of school, family and community in environmental and legal education of schoolchildren, as well as the development of general theoretical and general didactic bases of education on the subject;

- modeling the improvement of cooperation between school, family and community in environmental and legal education of schoolchildren, substantiating it on the example of scientific and theoretical experiments;

- proposing and implementing a system that meets modern requirements and takes into account the principles of continuing education by improving the cooperation of school, family and community in environmental and legal education of secondary school students. The object of the study is the process of improving the cooperation of school, family and community in environmental and legal education of students, and 616 students from Surkhandarya, Tashkent regions and Tashkent city were involved in the pilot work. Methods used in the research topic: study of psychological, pedagogical, methodological, philosophical, social literature on the subject in the research process, DTS for general education schools, scientific-theoretical analysis of textbooks and manuals; comparative, pedagogical observation, surveys, interviews, questionnaires, tests, interviews, pedagogical experimental results and analyzed using mathematical-statistical methods.

The scientific novelty of the research topic is:

- based on the theory of education, based on the latest achievements of psychology and pedagogy, as well as ethnopedagogy in improving the cooperation of school, family and community in environmental and legal education of schoolchildren, developed innovative approaches based on its content and the formation of environmental and legal education;

- the pedagogy of such words as "education", "environmental education", "legal education", "environmental legal education", "environmental spirituality", "environmental legal culture", "environmental legal education", "environmental legal thinking" The essence of the analysis of technologies to ensure the effectiveness of practical training in environmental and legal education of students and the integration of the system of professional competencies has been improved on the basis of diagnostic design and priority of modular education;

- the analysis of the process of perfection of the student's personality through the improvement of cooperation in environmental and legal education, self-correction and emotional-value relations in accordance with the specialty, career-oriented, systematized and programmed information;

The practical results of the study are as follows:

- the importance and content of the use of school, family and community cooperation in environmental and legal education of secondary school students is pedagogically explained;

- the technology of modern development of a systematic approach to improving the cooperation of school, family and community in environmental and legal education of students, such as dialogue, roundtable, lecture, exhibition, seminar, conference, debate, practical training, competition;

- a modern model of improving the cooperation of school, family and community in environmental and legal education of students and its importance, study of relevant sources, practical training, demonstrations, exhibitions, excursions, "Cognitive Map", "Brainstorming", "Cluster", "Boomerang" methods have been identified;

The scientific significance of the research results As a result of the research contributes to the scientific and theoretical development of pedagogy in improving the cooperation of school, family and community in environmental and legal education of secondary school students. It is also explained by the fact that it can

be used effectively in the organization of special programs on the pages of television and the media. Introduction of research results: On the basis of scientific results obtained on improving the cooperation of school, family and community in environmental and legal education of students:

When we talk about the research work "Scientific and theoretical issues of improving the cooperation of school, family and community in environmental education," it highlights the historical significance of school, family and community cooperation in environmental education in the legacy of Eastern thinkers. Attempts have been made to reveal the importance of using the national values of our people, the views and teachings of famous scientists and thinkers in this area in the process of forming concepts for its improvement. Based on the above considerations, the following conclusions, suggestions and recommendations were substantiated:

Thus, in addition to recommending the following, increase the role of the media in providing environmental legal information in the formation of environmental legal awareness and environmental legal culture, improving the cooperation of school, family and community, the formation of concepts of environmental legal education, innovative methods of environmental legal advocacy and online use should be regulated. In this regard, in order to ensure the continuity of environmental legal education and upbringing in cooperation with the family and the community, to further improve the program "Family-neighborhood-educational institution" in all mahallas, to hold a competition "My prosperous neighborhood", "Environment and Youth", "We are responsible for the future", "Ecology and youth" should become a necessary opportunity.

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